

Studies on Hydrous Zirconium Oxide. Part-III. Electrophoretic Behaviour of Anions on Hydrous Zirconium Oxide impregnated Papers

ASIT K. SEN*, SUDHANGSU B. DAS and UDAY C. GHOSH**

Department of Chemistry, Visva-Bharati, Santiniketan-731 235

Manuscript received 30 May 1986, accepted 6 July 1987

Electrochromatographic studies of some anions on hydrous zirconium oxide impregnated papers have been carried out. Five background electrolytes of different pH were used for these studies at fixed potential differences and time intervals. On the basis of the differential mobility of the anions, which depends on the ion-exchange properties of hydrous zirconium oxide and the nature of complexes formed with the electrolytes, some useful binary and ternary separations have been achieved. Quantitative separation of microgram amount of Cr^{VI} from some binary mixtures of metal ions has been achieved.

ELECTROCHROMATOGRAPHIC studies of some cations and anions using hydrous stannic oxide^{1,2} impregnated papers have been reported from our laboratory. Some useful and highly selective separations of cations present in a binary and multi-component mixtures and anions present in binary mixtures have been observed. Similarly, hydrous zirconium oxide acts as a cation-exchanger^{3,4} as well as an anion-exchanger⁵⁻⁹. It has been proved useful in paper^{10,11}, thin layer⁴ and column chromatography^{6,11}. All these results have given us impetus to extend our work to the study of electrochromatographic behaviour of some anions on hydrous zirconium oxide impregnated paper. In this paper, electrochromatographic behaviour of anions on hydrous zirconium oxide impregnated paper is discussed. The same operation was repeated with ordinary Whatman no. 1 paper to find the role of the ion-exchanger under an electrical potential on the migration of anions. Thus some difficult and interesting separations of anions are reported.

Experimental

Electrophoresis was carried out in a Optronics EPR 550 horizontal apparatus. pH measurements were made with a Elico LI 10T pH meter.

All reagents were either G.R. (E. Merck) or AnalaR grade. Whatman no. 1 chromatographic paper (40×2.5 cm) was used for electrophoretic work.

Preparation of hydrous zirconium oxide impregnated papers: Paper strips were first soaked with freshly prepared 0.1M aqueous zirconyl chloride solution in 0.1M HCl for 10 s, and the excess being

removed by blotting and the strips dried at room temperature. The dried strips were then passed through 1M aqueous ammonia solution for 10 s and the excess again removed by blotting and then dried horizontally at $100 \pm 5^\circ$ for 1 h in an air-oven. Ordinary Whatman paper strips were also dried in an air-oven at $100 \pm 5^\circ$ for 1 h for better comparison. The dried papers were washed several times with double-deionised water and finally dried at room temperature before use.

Anion solutions: Aqueous solution of sodium, potassium or ammonium salts of the anions under investigation were prepared (anion, 2–4 mg ml⁻¹).

Background electrolytes: Five background electrolytes were used for electrochromatographic studies, (i) 0.05M HCl+0.09M KCl (pH 2), (ii) 0.2M CH_3COOH +0.2M CH_3COONa (pH 4), (iii) 0.1M CH_3COOH +0.1M CH_3COONa (pH 6), (iv) 0.1M NH_4OH +0.1M NH_4Cl (pH 8), and (v) 0.1M NH_4OH +0.1M NH_4Cl (pH 10).

Detection reagents: The following detection reagents were used: (i) CrO_4^{2-} : 1% ethanolic diphenyl carbazide solution, (ii) PO_4^{3-} , AsO_4^{3-} : 4.5% solution of ammonium molybdate in HNO_3 , (iii) $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{4-}$, SCN^- : 4% FeCl_3 in 0.01M HCl solution, (iv) $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}$: 4% FeSO_4 in 0.01M H_2SO_4 solution, (v) VO_3^- : 20% H_2SO_4 +1% H_2O_2 , (vi) WO_4^{2-} : 25% SnCl_2 solution in concentrated HCl, (vii) MoO_4^{2-} : 5% SnCl_2 in 6M HCl+10% KCNS, and (viii) I^- : chlorine water+starch suspension.

Procedure: The electrode vessels after washing several times with distilled water were filled with equal volumes of aqueous background electrolytes (300 ml). The electrophoresis was then carried out

** Chemistry Department, Durgapur Govt. College, Durgapur.

by the usual procedure¹. A potential difference of 250 V was applied for 1 h. The migration of anions was determined by measuring the spot from the point of application to the middle of the zone. On the basis of the results observed in the case of individual anions, the experiment was repeated with synthetic binary or ternary mixtures of anions of interest for separations.

For quantitative work a standard stock solution of Cr^{VI} (6 mg ml⁻¹) was prepared. The known amount of synthetic mixture containing Cr^{VI} was applied with the help of a micropipette on the centre of line of application of impregnated paper. The electrophoresis was then carried out using solution (i) of pH 2 as background electrolyte. A pilot experiment was run simultaneously to locate the position of Cr^{VI}. The area corresponding to Cr^{VI} was then cut from the electrochromatographic paper and eluted by 20 ml of 2M KOH solution⁶. Cr^{VI} was then determined spectrophotometrically by diphenyl carbazide method¹². Each experiment was repeated thrice to check reproducibility and the results are shown in Table 3.

Results and Discussion

In the studies, electrophoretic migration of anions in combination with the exchange property of hydrous zirconium oxide yield a number of important separations. The migration of an anion is the distance of the centre of the spot from the middle of the paper where it is applied originally. A plus sign is used for the distance travelled by the ions towards the anode and a minus sign for distance migrated towards the cathode. The mark 0.0 indicates no migration of ion under the specified conditions.

Electrochromatographic behaviour of some differently charged anions has been studied at

different pH using five background electrolytes on hydrous zirconium oxide impregnated papers as well as on ordinary Whatman no. 1 papers for comparison (Table 1). The exchanger material is sparingly soluble in background electrolytes used in the experiment. The migration of anions on ordinary Whatman no. 1 papers are given in parentheses in Table 1. The rate of migration on an impregnated paper under a given potential difference depends on the size and charge of the components, relative molecular mass, electrolyte concentration and adsorption on the exchanger.

Hydrous zirconium oxide behaves as an anion-exchanger in acidic medium and its anion-exchange property decreases with increase of pH. This is evident with the increasing migration of CrO₄²⁻ at pH 2, 4 and 6. Again its increment in migration is continued with the increase of pH from 8 to 10. Strongly adsorbed anions have no migration or low rate of migration. The migration values of AsO₄³⁻, PO₄³⁻, WO₄²⁻, MoO₄²⁻ and VO₃⁻ on impregnated papers are zero at low pH which might be either due to strong adsorption or due to insoluble salt formation.

From Table 1, it is evident that the anions which are not strongly adsorbed can be separated from various other anions. Some useful binary and ternary separations are given in Table 2. The figure within parentheses denotes the distance travelled by the anions. The binary anion separations which are achieved on both ordinary Whatman papers and impregnated papers are not shown. From the above results it seems that electrophoresis on hydrous zirconium oxide impregnated paper is of value in certain analytical separations that are not feasible on ordinary Whatman no. 1 papers.

On the basis of electrophoretic mobilities of anions and cations⁴ on hydrous zirconium oxide

TABLE 1—MOVEMENT (cm)* OF IONS IN VARIOUS ELECTROLYTES ON HYDRATED ZIRCONIUM OXIDE PAPERS AND ON ORDINARY WHATMAN NO. 1 PAPERS

Time=1 h, Voltage applied=250 V

Metal ion	0.9 M KCl	0.2 M	0.1 M	0.1 M NH ₄ OH	0.1 M NH ₄ OH
	+ 0.05 M HCl	CH ₃ COOH + 0.2 M CH ₃ COONa	CH ₃ COOH + 0.1 M CH ₃ COONa	+ 0.1 M NH ₄ Cl	+ 0.1 M NH ₄ Cl
	pH 2	pH 4	pH 6	pH 8	pH 10
CrO ₄ ²⁻	0.0(+3.5)	+1.0(+6.5)	+1.2(+6.3)	0.0(+4.2)	+3.6(+6.0)
Fe(CN) ₆ ³⁻	+3.0(+4.0)	+5.0(+10.0)	+3.3(+6.2)	+3.3(+5.3)	+5.5(+6.9)
Fe(CN) ₆ ⁴⁻	+3.0(+4.0)	T(+7.0)	+3.2(+5.6)	+3.2(+5.0)	+4.5(+5.7)
SON ⁻	D	+5.0(+8.0)	+5.0(+7.6)	+4.0(+7.0)	+5.0(+6.8)
PO ₄ ³⁻	0.0(0.0)	0.0(+4.8)	0.0(+2.5)	0.0(+2.4)	0.0(+3.2)
AsO ₄ ³⁻	0.0(0.0)	0.0(+3.6)	0.0(+3.2)	- (-)	- (-)
VO ₃ ⁻	0.0(+1.8)	0.0(+6.8)	0.0(+4.5)	0.0(+3.0)	0.0(+4.9)
MoO ₄ ²⁻	0.0(+0.5)	0.0(T)	+0.8(+5.0)	0.0(+3.0)	+3.0(+6.5)
WO ₄ ²⁻	0.0(+2.5)	0.0(+4.5)	+0.0(+0.2)	0.0(+3.3)	+2.8(+8.2)
I ⁻	+1.5(+1.5)	- (-)	+5.0(+6.1)	+6.2(+7.0)	+5.5(+8.0)

*Values on ordinary Whatman paper in parenthesis.

D=decomposed. T= tailing

TABLE 2—SEPARATIONS ACHIEVED ON HYDROUS ZIRCONIUM OXIDE IMPREGNATED PAPER BY ELECTROPHORESIS

Background electrolyte	Separations achieved (cm)
0.09 M KCl + 0.05 M HCl (pH 2)	$\text{CrO}_4^{2-}(0.0) - \text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{4-}(+2.9)/\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}(+3.0) ; \text{VO}_5^{2-}(0.0) - \text{I}^{-}(+1.5)$
0.2 M $\text{CH}_3\text{COOH} + 0.2$ M CH_3COONa (pH 4)	$\text{CrO}_4^{2-}(+0.8)/\text{VO}_5^{2-}(0.0)/\text{MoO}_4^{2-}(0.0) - \text{SON}^{-}(+4.9)$
0.1 M $\text{CH}_3\text{COOH} + 0.1$ M CH_3COONa (pH 6)	$\text{CrO}_4^{2-}(+1.0) - \text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{4-}(+3.0)/\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}(+3.0)/\text{SON}^{-}(+3.0)$ $\text{MoO}_4^{2-}(+0.83) - \text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{4-}(+3.2)/\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}(+3.0)/\text{SON}^{-}(+3.5)$ $\text{VO}_5^{2-}(0.0) - \text{CrO}_4^{2-}(+1.5)/\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{4-}(+3.0)$
0.1 M $\text{NH}_4\text{OH} + 0.1$ M NH_4Cl (pH 8)	$\text{CrO}_4^{2-}(0.0) - \text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{4-}(+3.5)/\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}(+3.4)/\text{SON}^{-}(+3.9) - \text{I}^{-}(+6.2)$ $\text{WO}_4^{2-}(0.0) - \text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{4-}(+3.5)/\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}(+3.2)/\text{SON}^{-}(+4.0) - \text{I}^{-}(+6.3)$ $\text{PO}_4^{3-}(0.0) - \text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{4-}(+3.4)/\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}(+3.2)/\text{SON}^{-}(+3.8) - \text{I}^{-}(+6.1)$ $\text{VO}_5^{2-}(0.0) - \text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{4-}(+3.3)/\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}(+3.0)/\text{SON}^{-}(+3.8) - \text{I}^{-}(+6.2)$ $\text{MoO}_4^{2-}(0.0) - \text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{4-}(+3.3)/\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}(+3.1)/\text{SON}^{-}(+3.7) - \text{I}^{-}(+6.0)$
0.1 M $\text{NH}_4\text{OH} + 0.1$ M NH_4Cl (pH 10)	$\text{VO}_5^{2-}(0.0) - \text{MoO}_4^{2-}(+2.5)/\text{WO}_4^{2-}(+2.4)/\text{CrO}_4^{2-}(+2.5) - \text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{4-}(+3.9)/$ $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}(+3.4)/\text{SON}^{-}(+3.9)/\text{I}^{-}(+4.5)$ $\text{PO}_4^{3-}(0.0) - \text{MoO}_4^{2-}(+2.5)/\text{WO}_4^{2-}(+2.3)/\text{CrO}_4^{2-}(+2.4) - \text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{4-}(+3.7)/$ $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}(+3.7)/\text{SON}^{-}(+4.0)/\text{I}^{-}(+4.5)$

impregnated paper, quantitative separation of Cr^{VI} from some binary mixtures using background electrolyte solution (i) of pH 2 has been carried out (Table 3). Using this technique, V^{V} , Mo^{VI} and W^{VI} can also be separated from several other binary mixtures of metal ions at pH 2. It is evident from $\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}} - \text{Fe}^{\text{III}}$ separation that the method can be

utilised for the estimation of chromium in chrome iron ores.

Acknowledgement

The authors wish to express their thanks to Prof. A. K. De, Head, Department of Chemistry, Visva-Bharati, for encouragement. The financial assistance of U.G.C., New Delhi, is sincerely acknowledged.

 TABLE 3—QUANTITATIVE SEPARATION OF Cr^{VI} FROM BINARY MIXTURES ON HYDROUS ZIRCONIUM OXIDE IMPREGNATED PAPER

Voltage applied = 250 V, Time = 2 h,		Background electrolyte = 0.05 M HCl + 0.09 M KCl (pH 2)		
Serial no.	Mixture taken*	Amount of the other metal ion applied	Amount of Cr^{VI} recovered**	Standard deviation
		μg	μg	
1.	Cr^{VI}	—	6.1	± 0.8
2.	$\text{Cr}^{\text{IV}} - \text{Hg}^{\text{II}}$	Hg^{II} (5.0)	6.0	± 0.16
3.	$\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}} - \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}$	Cu^{II} (5.2)	6.0	± 0.16
4.	$\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}} - \text{Fe}^{\text{III}}$	Fe^{III} (3.0)	5.97	± 0.17
5.	$\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}} - \text{Mn}^{\text{II}}$	Mn^{II} (4.6)	6.0	± 0.16
6.	$\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}} - \text{Ni}^{\text{II}}$	Ni^{II} (6.2)	6.03	± 0.20
7.	$\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}} - \text{Co}^{\text{II}}$	Co^{II} (4.0)	5.87	± 0.33
8.	$\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}} - \text{UO}_2^{\text{II}}$	UO_2^{II} (4.9)	5.87	± 0.33
9.	$\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}} - \text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}$	Ce^{IV} (2.1)	6.0	± 0.16

* Cr^{VI} added in each experiment = 6 μg .

**Average value of three experimental observations.

References

1. A. K. SEN and R. K. GHATUARY, *Chromatographia*, 1979, **12**, 237.
2. A. K. SEN and U. C. GHOSH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, **56**, 863.
3. M. ABB, B. A. NASHIR and T. YOSHIKA, *J. Chromatogr.*, 1978, **153**, 295.
4. A. K. SEN, S. B. DAS and U. C. GHOSH, *J. Liq. Chromatogr.*, 1985, **8**, 2999.
5. S. FUSTANOWSKI, *J. Chromatogr.*, 1967, **31**, 266.
6. K. A. KRAUS, H. O. PHILLIPS, T. A. CARLSON and J. S. JOHNSON, "Proceedings of the Second United Nations International Conference on the Peaceful Uses of Atomic Energy", United Nations, Geneva, 1958, pp. 3-16.
7. A. K. SEN and U. C. GHOSH, *Indian J. Chem. Educat.*, 1981, **8**, 17.
8. A. K. SEN and U. C. GHOSH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, **57**, 103; 1981, **58**, 136.
9. N. J. SINGH and S. N. TANDON, *Talanta*, 1977, **24**, 459.
10. J. P. ADOLFF, *J. Chromatogr.*, 1961, **5**, 365.
11. N. J. SINGH and S. N. TANDON, *Chromatographia*, 1977, **10**, 309.
12. E. B. SANDELL, "Colorimetric Determination of Traces of Metals", 3rd. ed., Interscience, New York, 1955.